

Design and Analysis Workflows for Advanced Simulation of Composite Structures

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SUMMARY

This paper reviews the processes, methods and tools required to carry out advanced structural simulation of laminated composite structures, and presents examples of the design, modelling and analysis tasks within an integrated workflow. The analysis of key issues such as manufacturability, tolerances and optimisation is considered.

Keywords: Composites, finite element analysis, simulation, workflow, variability

INTRODUCTION

The increasing use of laminated composite materials in aerospace, wind energy and motorsport has led to a corresponding increase in the requirements for advanced structural analysis of composite components and assemblies. In addition, there is a demand to meet market pressures by designing and developing products faster and more efficiently.

The capabilities of design and analysis tools have advanced significantly in recent years and industrial users continually seek to optimise their design process and carry out reviews of the available systems. However, when considering the complex simulation tasks required in the design of laminated composite structures, it is useful to consider the use of design and simulation tools from a *workflow* perspective, rather than simply assessing individual capabilities of disparate products.

THE WORKFLOW APPROACH APPLIED TO COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

A workflow approach to the design and simulation of composite structures requires a set of tools that are integrated with each other and that are based on a coherent and consistent foundation throughout. Whilst graphical user-interfaces need not be identical at every stage, there should be an underlying consistency in terms of nomenclature and data format; information should persist from one step to the next in a sensible manner.

The workflow typically starts at the geometry definition stage, where the geometry is defined in CAD or other pre-processor. The geometry and assembly definitions are then fed into the analysis stage as standardised data.

For structures using composite construction there are then additional steps to be completed in order to define the composite materials and layups. The ply stack needs to be defined, with materials, thicknesses and orientations on all regions of the composite structure. For complex curved structures some form of draping analysis can be used to more precisely define the ply orientations and to assist in planning the manufacturing process.

Once an initial design has been completed, simulations are performed to validate and support the design. During the simulation tasks analysts often modify the ply stack, drop-offs, etc, and carry out optimisation of the ply stack to achieve specific targets (strength, mass, deflection) for specified loadcases.

While some linear analysis is often carried out at this stage, it is increasingly important for the performance of the design to be considered under a wider range of loadcases that can give rise to a nonlinear response, such as drop-test and crash events. To fully understand the ultimate capacity of the structure, nonlinear effects such as damage and failure are needed. This could result in the additional transfer of the structural model to a nonlinear analysis code and potentially to another set of users.

The results of both linear and nonlinear analysis may be used to determine whether further modifications are required to the design. Sometimes these design changes are carried out by the analyst, who will then return the modified definition to the designer. At other times, the analyst will simply tell the designer what needs to be changed and the designer will make the changes.

Once a design has been finalised it is important to consider in detail how the structure will be manufactured. The design definition, with the associated layup information, is imported into a manufacturing simulation where tape-laying or other processes can be simulated.

The workflow that has just been described follows a natural design process starting from CAD geometry, taking into consideration detailed composite design, ply-stack definition, structural simulation, optimisation, and manufacturing simulation. Smaller iterative loops within the workflow enable analysts and designers to refine the definition in order to meet specific performance or manufacturing targets.

The workflow is illustrated in more detail in the following sections, using a wind turbine blade as an example model. The toolset used in this example is the CATIA Composites workbench, with additional Dassault Systèmes products from the SIMULIA and DELMIA brands.

WORKFLOW SEQUENCE

The workflow sequence is roughly broken down into the following steps:

- Structural assembly in CAD
- Composite ply layup and sequencing
- Structural analysis
- Manufacturing

While we are presenting this workflow as a sequence, in practice there is often a significant number of iterations during which the design gets passed back and forth between stages until it reaches maturity.

Structural Assembly in CAD

The first stage is to create the product design and definition. This includes creation of the geometry as well as establishing the structural assembly and the definition of the composite materials and layup data. Historically, the challenge in this phase has been to handle the large amount of data and to cope with the lack of integration with other tools that are used for design mock-ups.

Using a fully featured composites workbench that is integrated into a complete CAD system enables an early conceptual definition of the various composites parts to be completed within the context of the overall assembly. In addition, the composites workbench provides tools that enable the straightforward management of the composite material definitions.

In our turbine blade example the composite surfaces are divided into a grid, which matches the underlying structures that act as reference elements underpinning the wing panel design (in this case the ribs and spars). Also included in the initial CAD definition is the specification of various constraints that can be inferred from these reference elements, such as clearance, slope rates and drop-off strategies.

In this example the grid cells are created for each region of the upper blade panel and are delineated by a set of spars and ribs, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Initial CAD defined on a reference grid

Ply Stacking Definition

The next stage is to refine the stacking definition. This can be a complex task, so an important aspect of the toolset is the straightforward management of the composites data through an intuitive ply stacking tool.

In CATIA, the Virtual Stacking Management tool helps refine the stacking sequences for each of the predefined cells. As shown in Figure 2 the user has access to a variety of data, including cell names, thicknesses, and number of plies. Through this GUI, the designer can define some initial stacking rules, such as symmetry and balanced layups, and reassign plies to other cells in order to optimise the ply shapes.

Figure 2 Virtual stacking management

While the grid approach is useful in this preliminary phase to define the virtual stacking sequence and constraints, there is a need for further options to optimise the construction including the use of a variety of algorithms to set optimal drop-off patterns, or to minimise the ply overlaps.

At this stage the designer can move to a more detailed approach to tailor the design by swapping ply edges interactively in order to optimize ply shapes and drop-offs, as shown in Figure 3, or by rerouting sets of plies along a preferred path.

The user can also add more plies manually, including adhesive layers or bonding strips, and define the parameters of core inserts for sandwich constructions.

Figure 3 Investigation of ply overlaps

After finalising the initial ply definition the designer can produce a top surface geometry that matches the thickness of the stack across the component (Figure 4). This

will be important for later construction of finite element models where the true top and bottom surfaces of the laminated structure are required.

Figure 4 Final surface definition after assembly of the ply stack

Throughout these phases the toolset needs to provide dedicated data query features - such as core sampling - which can be used to check the details of the ply stack at selected locations and to provide data on thickness and layup, as well as obtain estimates of mass, volume, center of gravity and other standard information.

These design checks can be visualized interactively and can also be stored with the main CAD feature tree for subsequent review, or exported to external files for reuse by other in-house applications.

Composite Structural Analysis

The design information developed in the first steps of the workflow provides the basis for advanced simulation of the structure. In order to evaluate the performance of the composite structure under a variety of loading conditions, it is typically necessary to perform nonlinear simulations.

Composites behave quite differently from metallic structures. For metallic structures linear finite element analysis can often provide results that are a sufficient basis for good design decisions particularly when combined with well-proven analytical stressing techniques. For composite structures, however, linear analysis can be limited in its applicability and supporting analytical methods are not as well-developed. In particular, the buckling and post-buckling response of composites can introduce complex failure modes which may not be taken into account appropriately in linear analysis.

Nonlinear analysis with advanced composite damage models is an important component of a good composites design product. For this example workflow the Abaqus finite element analysis (FEA) code is presented. It has advanced functionality in the areas of composites damage and failure, and is well integrated with the CATIA composites tools that were used for the geometry and initial design definition in the previous step.

Analysis Modelling

The first task in the analysis sequence is to bring the geometry and composites data from the CAD system into the analysis software. Composites Modeler for Abaqus/CAE (CMA), which is developed by Simulayt, can be used to transfer accurate fiber angles and ply thicknesses to the Abaqus/CAE modeling environment.

CMA offers a variety of advanced composites modeling tools including draping simulation and evaluation of flat pattern geometry.

The composites tools with the Abaqus/CAE environment can be used to apply the ply stack to the analysis geometry, to interrogate the ply-stack (as shown in Figure 5) and to add more advanced data such as damage and failure models.

Figure 5 Screenshot of Abaqus/CAE ply-stack plot

It is important at this stage that the fundamental structural data can be imported into the modeling system accurately and reliably and that the addition of more advanced modeling data can be carried out efficiently without having to modify any of the underlying material data and structural properties. This ensures that the workflow is continuous and that the underlying model definition remains consistent.

The execution of the nonlinear simulation can be controlled from within Abaqus/CAE, with monitoring tools that allow the analyst to follow the progress of the simulation.

Analysis Results Visualisation

The assessment of finite element results from advanced nonlinear analyses is a critical stage of the workflow. Analysis models are becoming larger and more complex, and the volume of output data is increasing significantly.

The analyst will typically use visualisation capabilities such as envelope plots to identify maximum or minimum values through a ply stack together with ply-by-ply contours of key results, such as stress or strain, to assess the response of the composite structure. Where the simulation model has been augmented to include evaluations of damage and failure the analyst will carry out further investigations of the state of the

material to identify regions where damage has initiated, to assess the degree of damage, and to highlight key areas where plies may have failed in one or more modes.

To illustrate this phase of the workflow a generic birdstrike analysis has been carried out on the wind turbine blade as show in Figure 6 and Figure 7.

Figure 6 Example birdstrike analysis

Figure 7 Initial configuration of bird and blade

The results assessments carried out after the analysis can include a wide variety of contour and X-Y plots;

- X-Y plots of through-thickness results such as S11 stress (Figure 8)
- A plot of the deformation with a cutting plane used to remove parts of the structure for easier visualization (Figure 9).
- An envelope plot to show the maximum or minimum value of a variable in any ply at that location (Figure 10), and which includes the option of displaying which plies have the maximum or minimum value of the variable in every element (Figure 11).
- Individual plies can be isolated and results contoured on that ply alone (Figure 12), with the remainder of the structure included but not contoured (Figure 13).

Figure 8 XY plot of through-thickness stress at a single element

Figure 9 View inside the blade using a cutting plane

Figure 10 Envelope plot of S11 stress

Figure 11 Envelope plot showing ply with maximum value

Figure 12 A single ply

Figure 13 Single ply results

The Analysis-Design Loop

Advanced simulations of composite damage and failure require specialist knowledge, so it is important that the workflow allows for both analysts and designers to work on the design.

It is not uncommon for hundreds of simulations to be performed on the composite design. These simulations could cover a variety of different loadcases, including those arising during manufacturing, transportation, installation and operation, together with unique events such as impact or the bird strike used in the visualisation example.

Whilst carrying out these simulations, the analyst may wish to evaluate the effect of adding or removing composite plies, changing ply orientations, changing locations for the ply drop-offs, or other design modifications. The aim is to develop a design which meets the design objectives under all the loading events, so it is important for the analyst to be able to use the simulation tools in an iterative manner, making changes and assessing the outcomes.

Once the analyst has completed the work with the modelling environment, the updated ply definitions can be imported back into CATIA for the designer to assess in terms of the other design strategies and constraints related to, for example, manufacturing or assembly. In a more traditional design process that does not use a consistent workflow and integrated tools this stage is often missing or is extremely problematic.

This process (as shown in Figure 14) may continue with several iterations between designer and analyst until an optimised design is reached. At that stage the designer will produce finalised ply books, and associated construction information to allow the component to be produced.

The interaction between designer and analyst is enabled through the *Composites Link for CATIA V5* tool, also developed by Simulayt. It allows designers and analysts to communicate effectively during the composites development process, saving time, improving product quality and preventing costly errors that may arise through the use of inconsistent modelling methods and excessive data translation.

Figure 14 The Design-Analysis Loop

Manufacturing

Whilst an acceptable design can be developed from the major part of the workflow, including advanced nonlinear analysis, there are other constraints which need to be considered before the design can be finalised. The manufacturing of the composite structure is an important step to be taken into account near the end of the design workflow.

In this example the manufacturing of the composite part can now be investigated using the DELMIA application, as shown in Figure 15. The full design data, including the ply stack definitions, is transferred from the CATIA composites workbench.

The objective of the manufacturing process simulation is to examine the tool path in order to optimise the deposition of material, and to confirm that the component can be processed in the rig, with no interference between the component, the tooling, or the fixtures and fittings.

Figure 15 Manufacturing simulation; the component in the rig with associated tooling

Manufacturing variability

The majority of the workflow described so far is based on the initial CAD geometry definition, which in most cases is defined at nominal dimensions.

One of the unique difficulties with composite materials is that they can exhibit variation in fiber angle and resin distribution. Composites can also exhibit a significant degree of deformation during curing which means that the dimensions and properties of the final component may vary considerably from the nominal and may vary from batch to batch. This can mean that the results from advanced nonlinear analysis may be valid only for a small set of the manufactured components. Difficulties may therefore arise during assembly and operation because tolerance variations have not been considered in the analysis and design phases.

In some cases the modifications in manufacturing process itself are used to account for the variability. Components may be constructed with additional sacrificial plies which are machined away to the correct dimension during assembly and shims and resin filler

may be used to fill gaps. However, if possible it is important for the design process also to take some variability into account. This can be achieved by repeating the structural simulations with variations in dimension that are commensurate with the expected manufacturing tolerances. Random distributions of key parameters can also be imposed on the simulation model, including thickness, material properties and fibre orientation.

While these exercises may require a significant number of analyses, it is certainly useful to evaluate the performance of the design even at just a few points in the design space. Tools such as Isight can be used to define a Design of Experiments process which can automatically vary certain model parameters, execute the analyses, and collate the results into a form suitable for easy assessment.

The Workflow Completed

It is not straightforward to construct a diagram of a composites design workflow – there are forward and backward steps and iterative loops superimposed on the main design process, with different users using a variety of tools, sometimes sequentially, sometimes in parallel.

However, it is important to examine the workflow as a whole and to confirm that the fundamental design data can persist throughout, and that modifications or additions that may need to occur during certain stages do not invalidate the original design.

The workflow illustrated here follows a consistent approach from CAD through design, analysis and manufacturing simulation, and can include consideration of variability if required.

The tools used during the workflow are not all in one product, nor even all from one vendor, but they present a well-integrated set that can be deployed effectively in a standard engineering design environment.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The idea of a design workflow has been described and the benefits of using a consistent design approach and persistent data model throughout a complex design process have been highlighted.

An example of a wind turbine blade has been used to show the various phases of the workflow and to demonstrate how an integrated set of design and analysis tools can be employed to maximum effect.